

High school teachers' skills in education

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Annotation. This article explains the main ideas about what teachers should be able to do. This text explains how a university teacher's skills and abilities are important in their role within the educational system and how it affects their interactions with students.

Keywords: skills; instructor; raising; teaching techniques at universities.

Образовательные способности учителей высшего учебного заведения

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассмотрены основные понятия компетенций преподавателя. Раскрывается сущность компетентности преподавателя вуза как субъекта образовательной системы и ключевого фактора его взаимоотношений со студентами.

Ключевые слова: компетентность; учитель; воспитание; высшее учебное заведение; педагогика высшей школы

One of the main features of Teacher's work is its subject matter. The goal of a university teacher is the student. The results of a teacher's work are reflected in the behavior, knowledge, morals, skills and habits of others. The student, the object of the teacher, is also the subject. Because the student also influences the teacher, analyzes and evaluates his work. The nature of a teacher's work depends simultaneously on time and space. Time regulated by class and time not regulated. Teachers' classroom activities are hourly, but extracurricular activities have no time limit. One of the main

factors for a teacher to work effectively is to acquire a body of expertise and general knowledge. A teacher's competence is determined by a sense of proportion, compassion, respect and a sense of accuracy towards his students. Educational skills are also determined by educational skills.

Because teaching is a popular occupation, it is sometimes neglected by young people looking to other careers. Teaching is a unique profession. This profession is not only popular, but also a rare one. Because I have many teachers, but I only remember one or two. They also play an important role in our lives. It is thanks to teachers that people acquire basic science and knowledge so that they can choose the right path in life. Teachers are the bearers of science and knowledge, without which there can be no progress and development. Athletes must not only have access to advanced technology that allows them to independently solve the tasks assigned to them, but they must also have access to key competencies, among which the ability to communicate occupies a special place.

Teaching is a responsible profession. Because teachers work with humans and it is impossible to make mistakes here. The mistake you made in this case, though not immediately, will surely have its consequences after some time. Teaching is a complicated profession. This complexity is due to his creativity. Teachers have to play different roles at the same time. In order to achieve the best work results, improve the quality of teaching and achieve the set goals, teachers in modern education should pay attention to their level of development. "The task of university teachers in modern society is expanding and becoming more complex. University teachers are no longer just lecturers who teach the basics of science. It reveals the necessity of education as the need to systematically and comprehensively acquire specialized skills while discovering one's own role and one's abilities in the natural and social worlds.

Mobilization skills are related to the development of a student's steady interest in learning, work and activities. Along with the desire for knowledge, the formation of a creative attitude towards the world. Successful social and cross-cultural adaptation of students depends on scientifically sound planning, organization, motivation for future professionals, and the quality of different lifestyles of students in the social and educational space of higher education. This is achieved through the high implementation of The faster students adjust to higher education, the more successful their participation in the new social and educational system in university social life will

be. Modern social experience in the field of psychology and pedagogical practice and theory dictates the need for self-education and self-development of teachers. The growth and volume of professional information has resulted in a moral "obsolescence" of educational knowledge, requiring teachers to systematically renew their professional education.

The spiritual image of the teacher is more important today than ever. So in many ways nation building begins with building new schools and training new teachers. Such teachers can educate and educate generations who can lead society to better and happier days. Every profession has its own principles in this regard, just as the teaching profession has its own. All teachers should follow these principles in their teaching activities. Teachers should not only recognize and understand the feelings, but also try to understand why and the context in which they arise. This ability is called "emotional clarity". The principle of patriotism is the most important principle of teachers' educational activities. He must devote all his educational activities to the strengthening and development of the country. Teachers must instill in their students a great and deep love for their country. Love for the Motherland begins with teaching the Motherland well, so regardless of the teacher's profession, the teacher must introduce the children to each mixture of the Motherland and give them sufficient information about it. Children must be introduced to the enemies of their country in the same way that teachers teach them to protect their country from enemies. Teachers must always stand by the people and the country with national enthusiasm. A teacher's improvement in the process of gaining practical experience should be based on a severely critical attitude towards the teacher's work and oneself.

Teacher self-sacrifice plays a key role in their constant desire for innovation in their daily work and creative activities. In other words, teachers must first empathize with their students and treat them with a single need. Solidarity and collectivism in teacher groups also affect student groups. Teachers must always protect their peers and foster mutual respect and respect among students. It is not proper for teachers to praise their own subjects and disparage others. The principle of solidarity requires that teachers among faculty members be honest and kind. He must not tolerate gangs, intrigues and individualism within the group. The principles of collectivism and solidarity are reflected in teachers' attitudes towards groups. For solidarity and collectivism to exist, there must be the right moral climate within the group. In this

case, there is cohesion and collectivism within the team, teachers feel no pain in criticism and self-criticism, and those who accept criticism engage in self-education to eliminate their shortcomings. Humanistic principles are an integral part of the teaching profession. Teachers must love and respect people, including their own education. Only with love can children be taught and taught the most difficult and painful things. Humanism is the close attention, consideration, and sensibility of a teacher to his or her students. The principles of humanism require teachers to care about the well-being of their students and to teach and educate them without hitting, cursing, or insulting them. ``Communicative competence is a set of qualities necessary for optimal interpersonal communication".

We can interpret the characteristics of the teaching profession as follows: It is a popular occupation in society. Because it is very important to teach and educate across generations. Therefore, an apprenticeship is always required. Because teaching is a popular occupation, it is sometimes neglected by young people looking to other careers. Teaching is a unique profession. This profession is not only popular, but also a rare one. Because I have many teachers, but I only remember one or two. They also play an important role in our lives. It is thanks to teachers that people acquire basic science and knowledge so that they can choose the right path in life. Teachers are the bearers of science and knowledge, without which there can be no progress and development. Teaching is a responsible profession. Because teachers work with humans and it is impossible to make mistakes here. Teaching is a complicated profession. This complexity is due to his creativity. Teachers have to play different roles at the same time. He works with different intonations, different gestures and movements. He speaks "in his own language" with his students. He communicates and interacts with students of different personalities. Teachers use only their own models, not ready-made recipes.

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